

QC Report - Agilent Technologies : 2 Color Gene Expression

QCMetrics InRange (8 of 11)

Date	Wednesday, August 11, 2010 - 12:17	BG Method	No Background
Image	US83403541_251897210116_S01 [1_3]	Background Detrend	On(FeatNCRRange, LoPass)
Protocol	GE2_105_Dec08 (Read Only)	Multiplicative Detrend	True
User Name	melblab	Dye Norm	Linear Lowess
Grid	US83403541_251897210116_S01_grid (from grid_file)	Linear DyeNorm Factor	0.399(Red)0.502(Green)
FE Version	10.5.1.1	Additive Error	5(Red)8(Green)

Sample(red/green)

Spot Finding of the Four Corners of the Array

Evaluate Grid

Feature	Local Background	
	Red	Green

	Red	Green	Red	Green
Non Uniform	0	0	4	1
Population	105	101	1439	643

Spatial Distribution of All Outliers on the Array

532 rows x 85 columns

FeatureNonUnif (Red or Green) = 0(0.00%)

GeneNonUnif (Red or Green) = 0 (0.000 %)

- BG NonUniform ● BG Population
- Red FeaturePopulation ● Red Feature NonUniform
- Green FeaturePopulation ● Green Feature NonUniform

Net Signal Statistics

Agilent SpikeIns:

	Red	Green
# Saturated Features	0	0
99% of Sig. Distrib.	463	799
50% of Sig. Distrib.	357	574
1% of Sig. Distrib.	231	382

Non-Control probes:

	Red	Green
# Saturated Features	0	0
99% of Sig. Distrib.	72240	46910
50% of Sig. Distrib.	431	592
1% of Sig. Distrib.	192	303

Red and Green Background Corrected Signals (Non-Control Inliers)

Features (NonCtrl) with BGSubSignals < 0: 16253 (Red); 19181 (Green)

Negative Control Stats

	Red	Green
Average Net Signals	327.32	538.37
StdDev Net Signals	8.50	9.10
Average BG Sub Signal	3.57	1.64
StdDev BG Sub Signal	8.65	9.35

Local Bkg (inliers)

	Red	Green
Number	43581	44377
Avg	54.82	25.87
SD	2.20	1.21

Foreground Surface Fit

	Red	Green
RMS_Fit	5.52	5.38
RMS_Resid	13.62	16.88
Avg_Fit	330.65	543.62

Reproducibility: %CV for Replicated Probes

Median %CV Signal (inliers)

	Non-Control probes		Agilent SpikeIns	
	Red	Green	Red	Green
BGSubSignal	12.43	12.29	-1.00	-1.00
ProcessedSignal	4.32	4.18	-1.00	-1.00

Array Uniformity: LogRatios

Non-Control Agilent SpikeIns

	Non-Control	Agilent SpikeIns
AbsAvgLogRatio	0.13	0.27
AverageS/N	7.35	3.93

Sensitivity: Agilent SpikeIns - Ratio of Signal to Background for 2 dimmest probes

(+)E1A_r60_n11		(+)E1A_r60_a97	
(g)	(r)	(g)	(r)
0.9	1.0	1.2	1.1

Spatial Distribution of Significantly Up-Regulated and Down-Regulated Features

#Up-Regulated:3055 (Red) ; #Down-Regulated:2405 (Green)

▲ Up-Regulated □ Down-Regulated

LogRatio Versus Log Processed Signal

Agilent SpikeIns Signal Statistics

Probe Name	Exp	Obs	SD	S/N
(+)E1A_r60_n9	-1.00	-0.19	0.05	3.61
(+)E1A_r60_a107	-0.48	***	***	***
(+)E1A_r60_a135	-0.48	-0.51	0.08	6.82
(+)E1A_r60_n11	-0.48	-0.06	0.11	0.60
(+)E1A_r60_1	0.00	-0.00	0.03	0.18
(+)E1A_r60_a20	0.00	***	***	***
(+)E1A_r60_3	0.48	-0.47	0.17	2.83
(+)E1A_r60_a104	0.48	-0.48	0.04	12.76
(+)E1A_r60_a97	0.48	0.19	0.14	1.35
(+)E1A_r60_a22	1.00	-0.23	0.07	3.26

Evaluation Metrics for GE2_QCMT_Dec08

Metric Name	Value	UpLim	LowLim	IsMandatory
AnyColorPrcntFeatNonUnif...	0.00	1.00	NA	False
absE1aObsVsExpCorr	0.00	NA	0.86	False
absE1aObsVsExpSlope	0.01	NA	0.85	False
gE1aMedCVBkSubSignal	-1.00	25.00	NA	False
gNegCtrlAveBGSubSig	1.64	10.00	-20.00	False
gNegCtrlSDevBGSubSig	9.35	15.00	NA	False
gNonCntrlMedCVBkSubSignal	12.29	25.00	NA	False
rE1aMedCVBkSubSignal	-1.00	25.00	NA	False
rNegCtrlAveBGSubSig	3.57	4.00	-20.00	False
rNegCtrlSDevBGSubSig	8.65	6.00	NA	False
rNonCntrlMedCVBkSubSignal	12.43	25.00	NA	False

◆ In Normal Range ◆ Evaluate

Agilent SpikeIns: % CV of Average BG Sub Signal

Median %CV: -1.00%(Red); -1.00%(Green)

Agilent SpikeIns: Expected LogRatio Vs Observed LogRatio

Y-Intercept = -0.220 ; Slope = -0.010 ; R² = 0.001